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- Shkelzen HASANAJ • Klaidi LOGU • Matilda LIKAJ
- Alfred NINI • Nertila DILAVERI • Flora GJONI
 - Adriana ANXHAKU • Irmela SHAMETAJ
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ART, A SOURCE OF LIFE AND RESILIENCE IN HARD TIMES

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ABSTRACT

This article examines art as a vital practice, addressing it not only as an aesthetic phenomenon but as a strategy for spiritual and cultural resilience in the context of existential uncertainty, social fragmentation, and identity crises. The study adopts an interdisciplinary approach that integrates the philosophy of art, analytic aesthetics, transformative pedagogy, cultural psychology, and heritage studies. Artistic creativity, experiences during the creative process, as well as aesthetic experience foster forms of analytical reflection, cultural mediation, and ethical formation in individuals, which are essential for the development of healthy life values. The article argues that art helps individuals and communities process trauma, reconstruct meaning in life, and preserve cultural continuity, even under conditions of social, economic, and symbolic crises. The role of education through artistic experiences is emphasized as a tool for intergenerational transmission, ethical awareness, and dialogical engagement, supporting life resilience. Moreover, cultural heritage is perceived as a regenerative factor within sustainable development strategies. The article proposes reconceptualizing art as a strategic component of cultural policies and educational systems, central to social cohesion and cultural sustainability.

Keywords: *Art as a vital practice, spiritual resilience, cultural heritage, art education, cultural policy, sustainable development*

Dr. Alfred NINI is a creator, educator, and expert in art and cultural heritage, with over 30 years of experience in artistic creation and university teaching. He has participated in conferences, published scientific articles, led artistic projects, organized national and international exhibitions, and serves as an external expert for ASCAL.

Introduction

This article has been developed by the author through independent analysis and interpretation of the role of art as a source of life and resilience in difficult times. Digital technology has been used only to improve grammar, clarity, and formatting. AI has not been used in the conceptualization, analysis, or interpretation of the findings.

In the context of contemporary social, economic, cultural, identity, and symbolic crises and concerns, art is increasingly being reconceptualized not merely as an aesthetic expression but as a vital practice with a direct impact on individual well-being and social cohesion (Dewey, 934; Nussbaum, 2010). The fragmentation of human experience, existential insecurity, the weakening or transformation of traditional institutions, and profound changes in the mechanisms of cultural transmission have highlighted the need for alternative approaches that support spiritual resilience, ethical orientation, and cultural continuity (Bauman, 2000; Frankl, 959).

In this new context, art, along with artistic and aesthetic experiences, functions as a space for reflection, mediation, and the reconstruction of meaning. It provides powerful spiritual resources for coping with trauma and anxiety, for rebuilding both individual and collective identity, and for reviving and articulating narratives of resilience and hope (Uçi, 2004). In this framework, art ceases to be merely a mirror of crisis and becomes an active, energizing, and transformative space, where human experience can be processed and reoriented toward a more stable and enduring inner equilibrium.

This article stems from extensive theoretical and practical reflection on the role of art in confronting contemporary

crises, as well as from an intertwined creative, pedagogical, and research experience in the fields of art, culture, and cultural heritage. The study does not treat art simply as an aesthetic activity or a formal creative process, but as a fundamental spiritual, ethical, and cognitive instrument, capable of guiding individuals and society under conditions of uncertainty, spiritual fragmentation, and crisis, contributing to the achievement of sustainable inner calm (Uçi, 2004).

The article adopts an interdisciplinary approach, drawing on the philosophy of art, aesthetics, analytical pedagogy, cultural psychology, and heritage studies. Within this integration of theoretical reflection and creative-pedagogical practice, art emerges as a unique life and social strategy. It not only fosters the spiritual development of the individual and strengthens social cohesion but also preserves and affirms cultural identity in times of uncertainty and profound societal transformation. Art is attributed to a transformative role, it enables the processing of existential experiences, the restoration of inner balance, and the reimagining of our relationship with the world around us (Kadare, 1993; Agolli, 2001; Plasari, 2005).

The central hypothesis of this article is that art, through the practical creative process and aesthetic experience, functions as a powerful mechanism for constructing meaning, restoring spiritual resilience, and fostering social dialogue (Caruth, 1996; Volkan, 2001). Art empowers the individual to understand the essence of reality and confront existential tensions, enables them to process personal and collective trauma, and to reformulate their relationship with themselves and the world around them through mechanisms of cultural and symbolic memory (Zeqo, 2007).

The aim of the study

The aim of this study is to analyze art as a source of life and resilience, conceptualizing it as an essential existential practice that supports the spiritual, ethical, and cultural development of individuals and communities under conditions of crisis and uncertainty (Dewey, 1934; Frankl, 1959; Uçi, 2004). Within the context of contemporary societies, characterized by accelerated social change, fragmentation of human experience, and the questioning of the value system of life, art is examined as an active space for the preservation of meaning, the reconstruction of identity, and inner resilience.

The article aims to analyze the role of art, artistic creativity, and aesthetic experience in processing experiences of crisis, articulating existential tensions, and constructing new life meanings, positioning art not as a passive reflection of reality but as a vital and transformative force. Particular attention is given to the role of art education and cultural heritage as mechanisms that foster social dialogue, strengthen intergenerational resilience, and contribute to the reconceptualization of art as a strategic component of contemporary cultural policies and educational systems, especially in periods when the very value of life calls for reaffirmation.

Theoretical framework

The concept of “*difficult times*” refers to historical and social periods of uncertainty, in which the fragmentation of values and crises of identity weaken traditional models of orientation (Bauman, 2000; Giddens, 1991). In the Albanian context, writers such as Ismail Kadare and Dritëro Agolli portray societies in transition and the tension between tradition and modernity (Kadare, 1999; Agolli, 2005).

Art functions as a tool for reflection and spiritual orientation. Dewey argues that aesthetic experience structures fragmented experience by integrating sensitivity, thought, and emotion (Dewey, 1934). The works of European artists such as Delacroix, Picasso, and Chagall demonstrate that visual art can engage the viewer with social change and collective memory.

From an ethical and pedagogical perspective, art and aesthetic education develop moral imagination and empathy, key capacities for solidarity and democratic functioning (Nussbaum, 2010; Freire, 1970). Freire emphasizes the importance of critical consciousness for personal and social transformation, and art creates symbolic spaces for examining and reflecting on lived experiences.

From a psychological perspective, art helps in processing trauma by providing a symbolic language for “*unpleasant*” experiences (Caruth, 1996; Laub 1992; Kadare, 1993; Agolli, 2005). The works of Kadare and Agolli mediate collective memory and historical trauma in Albania.

Greene emphasizes that art liberates the imagination, enabling the envisioning of social and ethical alternatives (Greene, 1995). In this way, art becomes a transformative mechanism that connects individual and collective experience, cultural heritage, and the need for innovation, contributing to the development of spiritual and cultural resilience in times of crisis.

Art in the context of “*Turbulent Times*”

The concept of “*turbulent times*” refers to historical and social periods characterized by structural uncertainty, the fragmentation of values, and identity

crises, in which traditional frameworks of meaning and guidance lose their stabilizing power (Bauman, 2000). Sociologist Zygmunt Bauman describes this condition through the idea of “*liquid modernity*,” where stability, belonging, and security are replaced by instability, enforced flexibility, and existential uncertainty. Similarly, Anthony Giddens emphasizes that late modernity is accompanied by a crisis of self-identity, in which individuals are compelled to continuously reconstruct their personal narratives (Giddens, 1991).

In this context, art assumes a role that goes beyond its aesthetic dimension, becoming a space for reflection, guidance, and spiritual engagement (Dewey, 1934). John Dewey argues that aesthetic experience provides a unique way of organizing fragmented experience, creating a meaningful whole that intertwines sensitivity, thought, and emotion. For Dewey, art is not separate from life but a deepened form of human experience that helps individuals understand and structure reality.

From both pedagogical and ethical perspectives, art and aesthetic education play a fundamental role in cultivating moral imagination and empathy, capacities that are essential for the healthy functioning of democratic and humane societies (Dewey, 1934). During times of crisis, these abilities become even more vital, enabling individuals to comprehend the experiences of others and to foster forms of solidarity that transcend cultural and social boundaries.

In critical pedagogy, Paulo Freire introduces the concept of analytical consciousness (*conscientização*), a process of critical reflection on reality as a prerequisite for personal and social transformation (Freire, 1970). Art

serves as a privileged medium for developing this consciousness, creating symbolic spaces where individuals can examine, question, and reformulate their experiences.

The psychological dimension of art in times of crisis has been extensively addressed by scholars of trauma and cultural memory (Caruth, 1996). Cathy Caruth notes that trauma often resists linear and rational narration, remaining “*unspeakable*” within traditional forms of communication. Through symbol, metaphor, and aesthetic narrative, art provides an alternative language for articulating and processing traumatic experiences. This process does not aim to erase trauma but to transform it into a form that can be experienced, understood, and integrated (Laub 1992).

From a philosophical and aesthetic perspective, Maxine Greene conceptualizes art as a force that “*liberates the imagination*,” allowing individuals to see the world not only as it is, but also as it might be (Greene, 1995). In times of fragmentation and polarization, this imaginative capacity becomes essential for the creation of ethical and social alternatives.

Within this expanded theoretical framework, art is understood as a transformative force that bridges the individual and the collective, emotional experience and critical reflection, as well as cultural heritage and the imperative for innovation (Dewey, 1934; Nussbaum, 2010; Greene, 1995). More than a mode of expression, art constitutes a distinctive way of knowing and inhabiting the world, contributing to the cultivation of spiritual and cultural resilience that enables individuals and communities to withstand, adapt to, and navigate periods of profound uncertainty and crisis.

Art as creative process and spiritual resilience

In contexts marked by existential uncertainty and multiple, overlapping crises, the creative process acquires a significance that extends beyond aesthetic production, emerging as a vital mechanism of spiritual resilience and the reconstruction of subjectivity (Dewey, 1934; Frankl, 1959; May, 1975). Artistic creativity provides a reflective space in which individuals can process fragmented experiences, articulate inner tensions, and reconfigure a sense of self in response to destabilizing realities.

John Dewey (1934) conceptualizes aesthetic experience as an integrative process that brings coherence and continuity to everyday life. From this perspective, art does not constitute an escape from reality but rather a heightened mode of engagement with it. Through the creative process, dispersed and disjointed experiences are transformed into meaningful structures, enabling individuals to establish a more stable and reflective relationship with both the world and themselves (Kadare, 1993; Agolli, 2001).

From an existential perspective, creativity and artistic experience can provide ways to confront anxiety, uncertainty, and loss, enabling spiritual growth when individuals find meaning and ways to articulate these experiences. In this context, art functions as an act of inner freedom, in which the subject does not passively submit to circumstances but actively reconfigures them through creation (Kadare, 1993; Agolli, 2001).

The creative process is particularly important in the processing of trauma. Studies by (Caruth 1996; Laub 1992) show that trauma often remains outside

traditional structures of rational narrative. Art, through metaphor, symbol, color, or rhythm, creates an “*other language*” that allows for the articulation of what cannot be said directly. This process does not aim at healing in the narrow therapeutic sense, but at the transformation of the traumatic experience into meaning, making it bearable and integrable into personal and collective narratives.

In this context, art emerges as a form of resistance against dehumanization, forgetting, and passivity. (Greene 1995) argues, art “*liberates the imagination*” and allows individuals to see beyond the constraints of the present. Creativity thus becomes an ethical and spiritual act, affirming the human capacity to construct meaning even under conditions of fragmentation and crisis.

Art, Education, and Cultural Heritage International Sustainability

The role of art as an educational and formative medium acquires particular significance in societies experiencing identity crises and rapid cultural transformations. Through artistic engagement, education extends beyond the mere transmission of technical knowledge and becomes a comprehensive process of ethical, aesthetic, and spiritual formation of the individual.

(Nussbaum, 2010) argues that education through the arts fosters moral imagination and the capacity for empathy, enabling individuals to comprehend the experiences of others and to cultivate more just and sensitive social relationships. In this context, art functions as an intergenerational bridge, transmitting not only aesthetic forms but also values, sensibilities, and collective memory across time.

From the perspective of cultural memory studies (Nora, 1989) emphasizes that collective memory requires tangible and symbolic forms to endure. Art, whether manifested through traditional heritage or contemporary practices, operates as *lieu de memories*, a site where the past is reinterpreted and rendered meaningful for the present. This process is inherently dynamic; as (Bhabha 1994) contends, cultural identity is continuously constructed, and art generates “*in-between spaces*” in which tradition and innovation engage in productive dialogue.

The integration of art into educational systems may also be understood as a form of resistance to the increasing reduction of education to utilitarian and instrumental logics. Eisner (2002) critiques the tendency of modern educational paradigms to privilege measurable outcomes, often at the expense of disciplines that cultivate imaginative, critical, and reflective modes of thinking. In times of social and cultural crisis, such capacities are not ancillary but fundamental to the formation of ethically responsible and critically aware citizens.

Within this framework, art and cultural heritage function as essential resources for cultural and social sustainability. They enable individuals and communities to maintain a sense of belonging and continuity, while simultaneously providing the conceptual and symbolic tools necessary to adapt to change and to renegotiate identity in conditions of ongoing transformation.

Art as Social and Intercultural Dialogue

In contemporary contexts marked by social polarization and cultural fragmentation, art functions as a powerful medium for dialogue between individuals and society.

As a form of non-verbal communication, it transcends language, political and ethnic boundaries, creating spaces in which diverse experiences can be shared, interpreted, and understood.

Geertz (1973) conceptualizes art as a “*cultural text*”, fundamentally open to multiple interpretations. This openness positions art as a meeting ground for diverse perspectives, fostering both dialogue and collective reflection. Empirical studies on reconciliation and peacebuilding show that community-based artistic practices can reduce prejudice and strengthen a sense of belonging (Boal 1992; Lederach 1997).

Metaphor and symbolic expression are central to this process. As Ricoeur (1976), notes, metaphor generates a “*surplus of meaning*”, enabling new approaches to reality. Consequently, art does not offer predetermined solutions; rather, it opens interpretive horizons that facilitate the construction of shared, sustainable, and resilient narratives.

Discussion and Conclusions

This article contributes to ongoing debates on artistic education and cultural policy by framing art and artistic creativity as fundamental mechanisms for fostering spiritual and social resilience. The analysis demonstrates that art represents a crucial dimension of cultural, spiritual, and social sustainability, particularly in times of turbulence. It serves simultaneously as a creative process, an educational tool, a carrier of cultural heritage, and a medium for dialogue, enabling individuals and communities to navigate the uncertainty and fragmentation of the contemporary world.

In conclusion, the article argues that art and artistic creativity, understood as experiential processes, should be

reimagined in policymaking as essential strategies for social and personal development, rather than as peripheral aesthetic luxuries. Integrating art into cultural policies, educational systems, and public services is vital for cultivating a more resilient, sensitive, and creative society, one that is better equipped to

face the complex challenges and crises of our time. In this perspective, art is not merely a reflection of reality; as a process-oriented experience, it becomes a transformative force that generates new and diverse meanings, contributing to a more humane present and future for both individuals and society.

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Guide for Authors

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Revista “Studime Sociale” botohet pa ndërprerje nga viti 1998. Ajo drejtohet nga bordi botues ndërkombëtar dhe botohet me kod ISSN, në dy forma: print dhe online. Artikujt mund të botohen në shqip ose anglisht.

Parimi bazë i botimit është rigoroziteti shkencor. Çdo artikull i nënshtrohet një recensionimi të verbër (**double-blind peer review**). Ai u jepet për recensionim dy studiuesve të fushave të afërta dhe artikulli botohet nëse recensat janë pozitive. Pra, detyra e përzgjedhjes së artikujve shkencorë është kompetencë ekskluzive e recensentëve anonimë.

Kostoja e revistës përballohet nga kontribuuesit sipas vëllimit të çdo artikulli (faqe me nga 2200 karaktere). Nëse ndonjë numër, apo artikull i veçantë i revistës, financohen nga ndonjë subjekt (individ apo institucion) në çdo rast bëhet shënimi përkatës.

Çdo artikull duhet të jetë në përputhje me standardet gjuhësore. Artikujt duhet të jenë krijime origjinale. Ato mund të jenë artikuj shkencorë ose recensionues. Artikujt shkencorë duhet të dërgohet në word me këtë strukturë: (1) titulli, deri në 15 fjalë; (2) autori/autorët (emri mbiemri); institucioni ku është/janë; adresat elektronike – për çdonjërin prej tyre; (3) përmbledhje (shqip), me 200-250 fjalë dhe 4-6 fjalë kyçe; (4) të dhëna për autorin/autorët, rreth 50 fjalë, si tekst; (5) teksti; (6) Referencat e plota, sipas rendit alfabetik të mbiemrave të autorëve; (7) abstract në anglisht (varianti anglisht i përmbledhjes).

Artikulli mund të shoqërohet me shënime në fund të faqes (footnotes) për ndonjë shpjegim të veçantë. Por ato nuk janë referenca. *Sistemi i referencave të revistës është sistemi i APA*, me referenca të shkurtuara përgjatë tekstit, shoqëruar me listën korresponduese të referencave të plota në fund të tekstit, sipas rendit alfabetik të mbiemrave të autorëve, apo institucioneve që kanë autorësinë.

Referencat e plota në fund të tekstit duhet të përbëjnë elementë (të dhëna) që të adresojnë te burimet origjinale:

- a. Për librat: autori/ose autorët (1); viti i botimit (2); titulli i librit, në korsiv (3); ku është botuar (4) dhe botuesi (5).
P.sh. Merton, Robert. 1968. *Social Theory and Social Structure*, New York: Free Press.
- b. Për artikuj nga revistat shkencore, kapituj librash etj.: autori/autorët (1); viti i botimit (2); titulli i artikullit, në thonjëza (3); titulli i revistës/përmbledhjes ku është botuar, në kursiv (4); revista apo botimi ku gjendet e faqet, nga-deri (5).
P.sh.: Buss, Loreta. 2010. “Childhood in Sociology and Society; The US Perspective”, *Currant Sociology*, Vol. 58, No. 2, pp. 355-350.
- c. Për dokumente arkivorë shtohet (pika 5) Arkivi, Dosja, fashikulli.
- d. Për dokumente të marrë nga interneti shtohet (pika 5) link-u dhe data e fundit kur është parë.

Referencat e plota, të listuara në fund të tekstit, duhet të korrespondojnë me referencat e shkurtuara nëpër tekst, të cilat vendosen si në shembujt: Për një autor: Weber (1998); (Weber, 1998: 156); ose Weber (1998: 156); Për dy dhe tre autorë: (Lazesfeld & Berelson, 1990) e (Olzak, Shanahan & West, 1986); Për më shumë se tre autorë: (Larsen ed al., 1989); për seritë e referencave (Blau, 1980; Kadare, 1995; Uçi, 2003; Pëllumbi, 2004; Omari, 1999). Në qoftë se për të njëjtin autor ka më shumë se një referencë në të njëjtin vit, atëherë shënohet: 2011a, 2011b.